

AN EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE QUALITY ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVE BONDING

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This paper describes the characteristics of an expert system devoted to the analysis and diagnostics of an assembly by adhesive bonding. The user interface uses a descriptive approach. The rules are split in public (general rules) and private (specific parameters) knowledge bases, to cope with confidentiality problems. The expert system shares data with dedicated data bases, concerning the adhesives characteristics, the substrates characteristics, and the description of typical assemblies as references. The expert system calls appropriate numerical programs, for the analytical evaluation of simple bond joint, or for the optimisation of the joint through finite elements analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the development of an expert system to support the design of an assembly by adhesive bonding of different materials.

The first aim of the expert system is not to choose the accurate adhesive, but to evaluate and criticise the process, to provide a diagnostic about the quality of the assembly. Knowing the physical and chemical characteristics of the substrates and adhesives (by consulting dedicated data bases), the specifications of the assembly and the productivity requirements (given by the user), the system advises the best suited processing conditions.

In order to achieve this goal, the expert system communicates with data bases (data over the adhesives characteristics, over the substrates), and also with numerical programs for the computation of the bond line performances.

The knowledge bases (the rules) are split into general bases, available for all the users, and dedicated bases, built by each user and usable only by him (to cope with confidentiality problems). This is done through a parameterised expert system: The general rules are the framework of the system, and dedicated information's, representing the confidential expertise of the company, are expressed as parameters, in independent factual knowledge bases.

As inputs to the expert system, the user has to:

- Identify the substrates and the adhesive, and describe the surface state of the substrates.
- Specify the mechanical properties required for the assembly.
- Give the working temperature and conditions.
- Describe the processing conditions considered.

As outputs, the user will get:

- The evaluation of the bond joint quality in terms of mechanical resistance.
- Advises over the accuracy of the chosen adhesive to meet the specifications.
- Description of the surface treatments and processing conditions required to optimise the performances of the assembly.

2. PRINCIPLES AND UTILITY OF THE EXPERT SYSTEM

2.1. The expert system: a step towards the simulation of the human reasoning

Computer science is divided into several development ways, one of those being the artificial intelligence. The best known artificial intelligence tools, that are slowly emerging from research world, and become available for industrial applications, are the expert systems. This chapter describes the mechanism of an expert system, compared with the one of a "conventional" computer program, and shows what the expert systems technology will provide to the resolution of industrial problems.

In a "classical" computer program, the inputs, provided by the user or by consultation of data bases, are used by an algorithm to solve a particular problem. The algorithm works on the input parameters, and gives values to output parameters, which are the solution of the problem. The sequence of operations is defined once for all by the programmer.

In an expert system, the heart of the program is a so-called "inference engine". This is not a pre-defined algorithm, dedicated to the resolution of one problem, but a rather general tool, designed to handle rules. Rules are generally written as follows (though they may have more sophisticated formulations in some cases):

*If (some conditions are fulfilled)
then (perform the following actions:...)
else (perform those other actions:...)*

Although this kind of reasoning may be taken into account by a "classical" software program, in an expert system, the links between the rules are not pre-defined. Rules are considered as data independent from the inference engine, which is able to decide which rule is to be taken into account instead of another (resolution of conflicts), and to find which rule will verify the conditions that are to be provided to another rule (backward chaining).

A simple example will illustrate this. In the expert system about adhesive bonding, the user is asked at the beginning to give parameters describing the problem. But during the expertise, the expert system will ask complementary information. Suppose that the adhesive chosen is an U.V. adhesive. The expert system has a rule stating that in this case, one of the substrates must be transparent. He asks to the user if at least one support is transparent. The user answers "yes". On the other hand, he has stated that the aspect of the surface must be perfect. The expert system will then activate another rule, and ask some other information to the user, to see if the adhesive is or must be transparent also.

This procedure (that is, the activation of one rule by another which does not have explicit relation with it), is easily handled by an expert system. Rules are stored in different knowledge bases, without explicit link, and one event in one knowledge base may activate another set of rules at any moment.

Finally, if the choices don't seem to give good results, the expert may help the designer to re-design the bond joint.

The re-design of the joint is likely to lead the designer, either to modify the specifications, or to choose another adhesive. In this case, a new reasoning loop will begin, which will integrate the information given in the previous loop and the modifications brought by the expert.

The first prototype of the expert system is designed to perform some of the tasks described here above and will be improved in the next version to close the loop. The tasks covered by now are:

- Acquisition and analysis of the specifications, provided by the user.
- Consulting of the materials data base for the acquisition of the characteristics of the adhesive and substrates chosen by the user.
- Computation of the mechanical properties of the joint line.
- Diagnostics on the quality of the assembly.

The selection of the adhesives compatible with the specifications is also partly covered by the prototype. This prototype will be tested on case studies, and the conclusions of those case studies will lead, besides the improving of the quality of existing rules, to the production of new rules dedicated to the advises given to the user in order to improve the quality of the assembly, and eventually to re-design the assembly.

3. INPUTS AND TOOLS USED BY THE EXPERT SYSTEM

3.1. Basic data provided by the user.

The first action to take is to provide the expert system with the minimum information he needs to be able to activate the rules. When the expertise is not computerised, this may be done through the filling of a kind of check list, which will give the first orientation to the definition of the problem.

In the same way, the expert system presents to the user, at the very beginning of the expertise, a check list by which it can get the information strictly needed in all the cases. The following describes this check list and the way it is presented to the user through the user interface of the expert system.

Anyway, all the fields of the check list must not be filled out for the system to work, but obviously, the more complete the data will be, the more accurate the diagnostics.

3.1.1. Identification of the adhesive and substrates.

The adhesives and the substrates are classified in a hierarchical way. Each adhesive belongs to a family (for instance, epoxys). The user is faced with a list of families, in which he will choose what he thinks to be the most appropriate one, and then the system displays, besides the list of families, the list of the adhesives belonging to this family. The user may decide not to select one adhesive, but to work with the general properties of the family.

For the two substrates, which may be the same or not, the structure is the same: a list of families (ferrous metals, non ferrous, thermoplastics, thermosets, glass, ceramics,...), and, for each family, the list of the materials belonging to the family.

This hierarchy helps to make the choice, and moreover, enables the system to retrieve the characteristics of the materials in the data bases, as we will see in the following section.

The surface state of the substrates is also defined by selection in one list of possible surface treatments.

3.1.2. Processing conditions.

The processing conditions specified by the user are required, either because the workshop does not offer other conditions (for instance, application temperatures), or to achieve a good productivity (bonding time).

The dimensions of the bond joint are given in terms of length, width and thickness.

Figure 2 shows the interactions between the times imposed by the process. The bonding (application of the substrates one against the other), must occur between the minimum open time

(which may be equal to zero, depending on the type of adhesive), and the maximum open time. Some time will be lost between the application and the possibility of handling the material, and the normal use of this assembly may only take place when the curing time is ended.

Figure 2

3.1.3. Mechanical constraints.

As it is sometimes difficult for the designer to give absolute values for the mechanical constraints to which the assembly is submitted, it is possible to define a level for all the different constraints.

3.1.4. Working conditions

Besides the mechanical specifications, the assembly may be faced with other constraints, such as hygrometry, acidity, temperature, and also to specifications concerning the electrical or acoustical insulation, quality of the surface aspect,...

3.2. Data bases

The structure of the data bases have been thought to allow the expert system to solve two kinds of problems:

- The hierarchical organisation of the adhesives and substrates data bases is such that, if some data are not available in the data base for the chosen adhesive, for instance, the corresponding data may be retrieved in the family to which the adhesive belongs. Of course, this analysis is always made while keeping in mind the safety point of view, so that an expertise made with the characteristics of the family instead of the actual characteristics of the adhesive, may seem pessimist.

- The possibility is open to the user to introduce his own data (which he wants to keep confidential), in a "private" data base, which will be consulted only when it is available, and which will allow the expert system to find dedicated solutions.

3.3. Bond joint Computation.

As it has already been said, the designer of the assembly is not always able to give the absolute values of all the mechanical constraints that will be applied to his assembly. The role of the expert system here, will be first to help the user to describe the kind of assembly. First, the user choose the appropriate shape of the bond joint. Then, he shows what are the types of constraints to which the assembly will have to resist. The expert system is at this moment able to say if the choice of the shape is the most accurate for the type of constraints.

The expert system calls a computation program, named LODIAC, which is able, in an analytical way, to estimate the resistance of the assembly. This software may work in two directions. Either the user knows the level of constraints, and specifies it to the system. Then, LODIAC will compute the required dimensions for the bond joint, with the substrates and adhesive chosen. Or the use doesn't know those values. Then, LODIAC, knowing the dimensions of the bond joint given in the "check list", will give the maximum level of constraints that the assembly may support.

4. FIELDS OF INVESTIGATIONS AND RESULTS.

This chapter tends to summarise the basic data provided to the expert system, the intermediate data, tables, and computations that the system will deliver, and the results that may be obtained. As already stated, different knowledge bases work in parallel, to get and verify the mechanical constraints, to verify the productivity requirements, and to analyse the compatibility between the substrates and the adhesive chosen. One important set of rules deals with the surface preparation. This knowledge base evaluates and compares the relative surface energies of the substrates and adhesive, activates rules depending on the substrate used to advise the best surface treatment, and makes use of characteristics of products found in little specific data bases (over solvents, primers,...).

<i>BASIC DATA</i>	<i>TRANSITORY DATA</i>	<i>RESULTS</i>
Adhesives: - Hierarchical classification - Composition - Loads	Correlation Tables: Adhesives ---- Substrates	Diagnostics, advises for the choice of the adhesive and surface treatment.
Substrates: - Hierarchical classification - Surface State. - Loads.	Correlation Tables: Surface prepa ---- Interfaces	
Processing Conditions: - Setting Time. - Drying Time. - Curing Time. - Joint Cond. Time - Surface of the bond joint. - Thickness of the bond j.	Knowledge base to insure that the processing conditions fit to productivity constraints. Dimensions Optimisation.	Advises to optimise the productivity
Specifications: - Average Temperature. - Environment. - Functionality of the joint. - Mechanical Constraints.	Constraints Quantification	Advises for a better dimensioning of the bond joint.

5. CONCLUSION

The expert system prototype helps to improve the design of assemblies by bonding. One of the first results it has brought in a research centre, where it has been built, is to provide correlation between the tests made in the testing laboratory, and the simulations performed by the system.

One other advantage of this approach, is that, even during the design of the expert system and the formalisation of the rules, it helped the experts themselves to give a more systematic aspect to the methodology they used to solve problems, to provide explanations to intuitive solutions, and so to generalise those solutions more widely.

The use of the expert system in the resolution of cases may also reduce the number of mechanical tests performed in the testing labs.

The next development related with this expert system, together with the expansion of the sets of rules by consulting other experts and the validation of the system on other case studies, will be to connect the expert system with a data base containing the results of mechanical tests performed on those case studies. The expert system could by this way be somewhat self learning by comparing the results of the tests with the results of the simulations.